

“DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF WALL PAINTING ROBOT”

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ABSTRACT

The primary aim of the project is to design, develop and implement Automatic Wall Painting Robot which helps to achieve low cost painting equipment. Despite the advances in robotics and its wide spreading applications, interior wall painting has shared little in research activities. The painting chemicals can cause hazards to the human painters such as eye and respiratory system problems. Also the nature of painting procedure that requires repeated work and hand rising makes it boring, time and effort consuming. When construction workers and robots are properly integrated in building tasks, the whole construction process can be better managed and savings in human labour and timing are obtained as a consequence. In addition, it would offer the opportunity to reduce or eliminate human exposure to difficult and hazardous environments, which would solve most of the problems connected with safety when many activities occur at the same time. These factors motivate the development of an automated robotic painting system.

Keywords: - Wall Painting Robot, Automation, Hazardous Environment

INTRODUCTION

The construction industry is a labor-intensive and hazardous business; the significance of construction robotics has emerged and is expanding quickly. The construction industry began utilizing robotics and automation in the early 1990s with the goal of improving safety, enhancing workspace perception, optimizing machine operations, and ensuring building occupants had a quality environment. Following this, the building industry saw a sharp increase in robotics and automation advancements. Even though robotics has advanced and has many uses, painting is still seen as a challenging task because the entire structure needs to

be painted. Automation in painting was invented to make this process safer, easier, and require fewer laborers.

The development of service robots became popular recently since the society needs robots to relax humans from tedious and dangerous jobs. In Egypt, as well as other developing countries, the increasing population stimulates the construction-related activities such as interior finishing and painting. Painting is classically done by humans and generally requires exhaustive physical efforts and involves exposure to dangerous chemicals.

Chemicals can seriously impair the vision, respiratory system, and general health of the human painter. These factors make painting an ideal candidate process for automation. More than 100,000 apartments are built annually in Egypt, with an average painting area of 40 million square meters (based on an average 100 m² apartment area with 400 m² painting area). The surface area of painting is more due to the renovation work and expected population increase in the future. This demand imposes challenges that will hardly be met using human painters only in the next decade. Therefore, development of a painting machine that can perform the painting task with minimum human intervention is needed and will improve the quality of painting. The need for an autonomous painting robot is both clear and strong.

Automated painting had been realized successfully in the automotive industry to paint millions of cars in the assembly lines. This industry uses spray painting, and the robotic system is fixed in the assembly line. The domestic painting robots should be different in the sense that robots should have mobility so that it can move to paint the fixed walls. Also, the domestic painter robots should use roller instead of spray which is the common practice in the market to attain customer satisfaction. Fast globalization and interconnectivity create the major driving force in creating and enhancing chance. Therefore, the society must acquire new trends of innovation to prosper in their ways of life. The community has revolutionized due to the interconnectivity greatly compared to some years back when usage of technology did not exist. Saving human labour numbers and timing are only the two main advantages; besides them we must consider the opportunity to reduce or eliminate human exposure to difficult and hazardous environments, and to improve the quality of such works which would solve most of the problems connected with safety when many activities occur at the same time.

Despite the advances in the robotics and its wide spreading applications, painting is also considered to be the difficult process as it also must paint the whole building. To make this work easier and safer and to reduce the number of labours automation in painting was introduced.

LITERATURE

Abdulrahman Yahya, Raed Abdulla, Syed Mohd Bahrin(1), Research have been conducted in the past regarding using automation for interior wall painting in the construction industry since exterior wall painting had been implemented in the construction industry. However, there has been no solid development due to certain gaps in ideology and technology. The nature of challenge for the automatic wall painting with multiple color will be to identify the dimensions of the wall, to ensure the painting of the entire wall, to ensure of having even coatings, thickness uniformity, and avoid any saturation, to ensure of keeping the paint inside the tank within a specific level of height, and to ensure to paint the wall with colors as desired. Therefore, the main aim for this research is to design and develop an automatic wall painting robot that is fast, precise, reliable, and helps to achieve low-cost painting operations. While the objectives is to: (i) design and develop a wheel-based robot with a spray gun system with multiple colors to paint the wall. (ii) design and develop a system for the spray gun to move horizontally and vertically. (iii) design a system to keep checking of paint level and send an alert. (iv) evaluate the reliability and efficiency of the system by investigating the consistency of the layers of paint along the whole surface. **P. Keerthanaa & K. Jeevitha(2)**, aimed to design, develop and implement a simple automatic wall painting robot. The robot was made of steel mobile platform and using conveyor shaft, spray gun & a controller unit that controls the entire operation of the robot. The system operated pneumatically so it needed an air tank or a compressor. Eventually the robot could perform painting for given dimensions of the wall using IR transmitter & receiver to detect the wall. But the pitfall was that the robot continued painting even after the wall ended.

Mohamed Abdellatif(3), Here the author described the working of the autonomous wall painting robot. The conceptual design of a movable painting robot is used for painting interior walls of residential building. The robot uses roller fed with liquid paint and keeps contact with the wall surface. The robot enables the roller to scan vertically as well as horizontally to the painted walls. The robot can makeover to adjust itself in front of the

wall. **Dhaval Thakar, Chetan P. Vora(4)**, In this paper they explained that the workers cannot manage robotic arrangement for higher efficiency so the rise of the such process had been made which is affordable, give better accuracy, consume minimum time for coating so they developed such mechanism which coat the object with the dipping technique having semiautomatic arrangement which is suitable and which can be valuable for small and medium scale industries. **Takuya Gokyu, Masayuki Takasu, Sumio Fukuda(5)**, the authors have shared that construction of Wall-Surface Operation Robot. plan to automate and increase the efficiency a series of restoration they plan to automate and increase the works by cleaning task. For the picture painting tile separation is done with single and multi-colour. **Pal Johan & Jan Tommy Gravdahl(6)**, here the author explained by increasing the speed in the standard manipulator. They used to identify the error in the direction which will not improve the quality of the paint. Then they explained that by keeping higher constant velocity throughout the orbit. **Aris et al(7)**, having 3DOF without considering those of the platform and a working envelope of (84x72x122 cm). Ceiling area of 46m² were painted in 3.5 hours which is 1.5 times faster than manual painting. However, this robot is bulky and has small workspace and designed to paint the ceiling only. **Kahane et al. and Warszawsky et al(8)**, developed a robot for interior finishing tasks of painting, plastering, tiling and masonry. They used a standard robot arm with 6 DOF (Degrees of Freedom) with 1.7 m reach and 30 kg payload. Their robot was mounted on 3 wheeled mobile robot which gives another 3 DOF. The robot can move between workstations and deploys four stabilizing legs at each site. This robot cannot be used in residential buildings due to its 500 kg heavy weight. A reduction in painting time of about 70% was reported for wall painting compared to human painting and claimed to increase extra 20% if ceil painting is included.

METHODOLOGY

Fig: 1 Methodology

DC MOTOR:-

The **DC Motor** or **Direct Current Motor** to give it its full title, is the most commonly used actuator for producing continuous movement and whose speed of rotation can easily be controlled, making them ideal for use in applications where speed control, servo type control, and/or positioning is required. A DC motor consists of two parts, a "Stator" which is the stationary part and a "Rotor" which is the rotating part.

Fig 2: DC Motor

BATTERY:-

Battery is an electro chemical cell which transfers chemical energy into electrical energy. An electric battery is device consisting of one or more electro chemical cells with an external connection provided to power electrical devices such as smart phone, torch lights, electric cars etc. A **battery** is a device consisting of one or more electrochemical cells that convert stored chemical energy into electrical energy. Since the invention of the first battery (or "voltaic pile") in 1800 by Alessandro Volta and especially since the technically improved Daniell cell in 1836, batteries have become a common power source for many household and industrial applications. According to a 2005 estimate, the worldwide battery industry generates US\$48 billion in sales each year, with 6% annual growth.

Fig 3: 12v 7.5Ah Battery

CENTRIFUGAL BLOWER :-

Apart from the industry-specific usage, the following are the most used in day-to-day life:

- Hairdryers
- Domestic extractor fans for kitchens and bathrooms
- Computer cooling fans
- Vacuum cleaners
- Roof ventilators

Fig 4: Centrifugal fan or blower parts

Fig 5: Arduino nano

MICROCONTROLLER ARDUINO NANO:-

There are multiple ways that the Arduino Nano can communicate with other microcontrollers, a computer, or another Arduino. Digital pins 0 (RX) and 1 (TX) of the ATmega328 provide UART TTL (5V) serial connection capabilities. This serial communication is channelled over USB by an FTDI FT232RL on the board, and a virtual serial port is provided to computer software by the FTDI drivers (which come with the Arduino software). Simple textual data can be transferred to and from the Arduino board using the serial monitor built into the Arduino software. When data is transferred to the computer through the FTDI chip and USB connection, the RX and TX LEDs on the board will flash (but not for serial communication on pins 0 and 1). A Serial Software.

4 CHANNEL 5V ARDUINO RELAY: -

A 5V 4-channel relay module is a relay module that contains four 5V relays together with the related switching and isolating parts. Interfacing with a sensor or microcontroller will be simple with the help of this relay module. Conveniently designed for regulating high voltage, high current loads such as electrical motors, lighting, AC loads, and solenoid valves, this relay module is a board. The primary purpose of this module is to interface with PIC, Arduino, and other microcontrollers.

Fig 6: 5V 4-channel relay module

Features & Specifications:

- The dimensions of this relay module are $L \times W \times H = 75 \times 55 \times 19.3$ mm.
- The relay module's PCB is blue in colour.
- There are four 3.1mm permanent screw holes on each corner of this relay module.
- There is one NO contact and one NC contact included.
- The voltage range in which it operates is 3.3V to 5V.
- It has a 5 mA trigger current.
- The relay's maximum contact voltage is 250 VAC (30 VDC).
- The current across all four relays is 70 mA and 300 mA when the single relay is operating.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP:-

Fig 7: Experimental Setup

C PROGRAMMING FOR EMBEDDED MICROCONTROLLER SYSTEM

CODE:-

```

int ir =8;

int relay1=2;
int relay2=3;
int relay3=4;
int relay4=5;
//int relay5=6;
int i;

void setup() {
  // put your setup code here, to run once:
  Serial.begin(9600); // serial communications
  pinMode(ir, INPUT);
  pinMode(relay1, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(relay2, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(relay3, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(relay4, OUTPUT);
  digitalWrite(relay1, LOW); //UP STR
  digitalWrite(relay2, LOW); //UP STR
  digitalWrite(relay3, LOW); //UP STR
  digitalWrite(relay4, LOW); //UP STR
  //pinMode(relay5, OUTPUT);

```

```

}

void loop() {
  // put your main code here, to run repeatedly:
  int state = digitalRead(ir);

  if (state ==1)

  {
    for(i=0; i<10; i++)
    {

      Serial.println("Painting");
      delay(500);
      digitalWrite(relay4,HIGH); // SPR ON
      Serial.println("spr on");
      delay(100);

      digitalWrite(relay1,HIGH); //UP STR
      Serial.println("up");
      delay(72000);
      digitalWrite(relay4,LOW); //SPR OFF
      Serial.println("srp off");

      digitalWrite(relay1,LOW); //UP STP

      delay(2000);

      digitalWrite(relay3,HIGH);// FW STR
      Serial.println("fwd");
      delay(500);
      digitalWrite(relay3,LOW);//FW STP

      delay(2000);

      digitalWrite(relay4,HIGH);// SPR ON
      Serial.println("spr on");

      digitalWrite(relay2,HIGH);// DOWN SRT
      Serial.println("dwn");

      delay(53 000);
      digitalWrite(relay4,LOW); //SPR OFF
      Serial.println("spr off");

      digitalWrite(relay2,LOW); //DOWN STP
      delay(2000);

      digitalWrite(relay3,HIGH);// FW STR
      Serial.println("fwd");

      delay(500);
      digitalWrite(relay3,LOW);//FW STP

      delay(2000);
    }
  }
}

```

```

}

}
else
{ Serial.println("Wall detection");

digitalWrite(relay1,LOW);
digitalWrite(relay2,LOW);
digitalWrite(relay3,LOW);
digitalWrite(relay4,LOW);
// digitalWrite(relay5,LOW);

}
}

```

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Quality of Painting: Assess the quality of the painted surface, including factors like evenness, coverage, and adherence to design specifications. Compare the results achieved by the robot to those of traditional manual methods. **Efficiency and Productivity:** Evaluate the speed and efficiency of the robot in completing painting tasks compared to manual methods. Discuss any improvements in productivity and cost-effectiveness. **Accuracy and Precision:** Analyze the robot's ability to paint complex designs accurately and precisely, including details such as edges and corners. Consider any adjustments or calibration needed to improve performance. **Versatility and Adaptability:** Discuss the robot's flexibility in handling different types of surfaces, textures, and painting materials. Evaluate its adaptability to various environments and project requirements. **Safety and Environmental Impact:** Highlight any safety features implemented in the robot to prevent accidents or damage to surrounding areas. Consider the environmental impact of using the robot compared to traditional painting methods, such as reduced waste or emissions.

CONCLUSION

- ❖ These robots offer a myriad of benefits, including enhanced efficiency, precision, consistency, safety, and customization.
- ❖ Improve the quality of paint application, and reduce the risks associated with manual painting methods.

- ❖ They also present challenges that need to be addressed, such as the need for advanced programming, regular maintenance, and skilled operators.
- ❖ Their impact on construction practices is poised to become even more profound, ushering in a new era of efficiency, quality, and safety in the painting industry.

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